

Microplastic Sampling Reference:

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2	http://hbj.hanzhong.gov.cn/hzsthjwz/gfgl/202307/7fab834025e24c13b00532d0ff1ef4a0.shtml
3	http://journals.caass.org.cn/nxxb/CN/10.11923/j.issn.2095-4050.cjas2022-0092#9
4	http://journals.caass.org.cn/nxxb/EN/article/updateBrowsCishu.do?articleid=60791&token=db8f6353dc1e403faf2e6e28abfaf23f&referer=https://cn.bing.com/
5	http://jyh.huangshi.gov.cn/pub/hsnyj/nyzx/xwdt/zwdt/202303/t20230302_994742.html
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8	http://s.union.360.cn/proxy.html
9	http://sthji.huangshi.gov.cn/zwgb/qtzdgknr/wjtz/202312/t20231211_1077816.html
10	http://tianqi.2345.com/plugin/widget/index.htm?s=3&z=3&t=0&v=0&d=3&bd=0&k=&f=808080&q=1&e=1&a=1&c=a7279&w=180&h=36&align=center
11	http://tjj.bynr.gov.cn/tjjztzl/tjgb/202305/t20230525_512598_senior.html?senior=true
12	http://tjj.jl.gov.cn/qt/login/?tradeResponse=%7B%22code%22%3A%22999999%22%2C%22message%22%3A%22%E6%9C%AA%E7%99%BB%E5%BD%95%22%7D
13	http://tjj.jl.gov.cn/qt/wzdb/
14	http://tjj.jl.gov.cn/tjsj/tjgb/ndgb/202307/t20230718_2429905.html
15	http://tjj.jl.gov.cn/tjsj/tjgb/ndgb/202307/t20230718_2430203.html
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